

A NOTE ON THE ESTIMATION OF ALUMINIUM BY ANTHRANILIC ACID

BY AJITSANKAR BHADURI

Anthranilic acid precipitates aluminium quantitatively as a dense, basic anthranilate. This fact has been utilised for the estimation of aluminium. The precipitate can be easily filtered and washed, and, on ignition, converted into alumina. The precipitation is completed at a pH of 4.6. The precipitate is, however, appreciably soluble in sodium acetate solution and also in the presence of much ammonium salts.

The precipitation can be effected either by (A) using sodium anthranilate solution, or by (B) boiling an acid solution of aluminium, containing anthranilic acid, with urea. Ammonia formed by the gradual hydrolysis of urea maintains the pH value of the solution between 4.2 and 4.6.

Method (A).—A solution of sodium anthranilate was prepared by dissolving anthranilic acid in 100 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution till the pH value of the latter was reduced to 5.4, using Bromocresol green as an indicator.

A solution containing about 0.1 g. of aluminium was neutralised with dilute ammonia till it became slightly turbid. The turbidity was removed by the addition of a very slight excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. The volume of the mixture was made up to 500 c.c., and a requisite quantity of sodium anthranilate solution was added to it till the pH became 4.6. Methyl orange was used as an indicator. A white voluminous precipitate was obtained. The mixture was then heated to boiling and afterwards cooled in ice-water. The precipitate was hereafter filtered through a Whatman filter paper No. 40. It was first washed with a solution containing 2 c.c. of the reagent for every 100 c.c. and then several times with cold water to remove the last traces of sodium anthranilate. The precipitate was ignited moist in a platinum crucible and weighed as Al_2O_3 . A solution of chemically pure potash alum was employed for analysis. Some of the results obtained are given below.

TABLE I

Al present.	Wt. of Al_2O_3 .	Al found.
0.02043 g.	0.03852 g.	0.02040 g.
0.02043	0.03857	0.02042
0.02452	0.04660	0.02460
0.04086	0.07714	0.04082
0.02043	0.03970	0.02047
0.01634	0.03070	0.01625
0.01021	0.01935	0.01025
0.03064	0.05786	0.03068

Method (B).—A solution containing about 0.1g. of aluminium was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate until it turned slightly turbid. The turbidity was removed by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid in very slight excess. The solution was made up to 500 c.c. and treated with a large excess of anthranilic acid (10-12 equivalents of Al present). Urea (4 g.) was then added to the solution and the mixture was heated to boiling till the precipitation became complete. This usually required more than an hour. The precipitate was allowed to settle in the cold and then filtered and washed as described under (A). Any precipitate adhering to the sides of the beaker was dissolved in a little dilute hydrochloric acid and from the solution aluminium was reprecipitated by the addition of ammonia using Methyl orange as an indicator. This was filtered through a separate small filter paper and washed with a solution of ammonium nitrate (2%). The precipitates were then ignited as described before. The results obtained are given below.

TABLE II

Al present.	Wt. of Al_2O_3 .	Al found.
0.02752 g.	0.07090 g.	0.02752 g.
0.02253	0.04260	0.02248
0.01878	0.03535	0.01872
0.01576	0.03524	0.01565
0.01878	0.03550	0.01878

It has already been stated that the presence of a large amount of ammonium salts retards the complete precipitation of aluminium. This is apparent from the following results.

TABLE III

Al_2O_3 present.	Ammonium salt added.	Al_2O_3 found.
0.01840 g.	NH_4Cl 5 g.	0.01130 g.
"	" 2	0.01590
"	" 1	0.01745
"	" 0.8	0.01780
"	" 0.4	0.01850
0.01840	NH_4NO_3 2	0.01480
"	" 1	0.01765
"	" 0.8	0.01770
0.01840	$(NH_4)_2SO_4$ 1	0.01870

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